

ON THE ROAD TO SUSTAINABILITY: PAVING THE WAY FOR
OPERAS AS AN EFFICIENT OPEN SOCIAL SCIENCES AND HUMANITIES
SCHOLARLY COMMUNICATION RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURE

Impact Monitoring Dashboard - Final

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ON THE ROAD TO SUSTAINABILITY: PAVING THE WAY FOR OPERAS AS AN EFFICIENT OPEN SOCIAL SCIENCES AND HUMANITIES SCHOLARLY COMMUNICATION RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURE

Deliverable 8.7

Impact Monitoring Dashboard - Final

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Abstract

This deliverable documents the evolution and final implementation of the OPERAS Impact Monitoring Dashboard within the OPERAS-PLUS project. Building on Deliverable 8.2 (2023)¹, it addresses previous limitations by integrating both performance monitoring and impact assessment into a single, user-friendly environment using Google Looker Studio. The report outlines methodological refinements inspired by the ESFRI policy brief on research infrastructure impact assessment, updates Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) to reflect strategic shifts, and describes the technical and organisational process of developing the final dashboard. By providing visual, accessible, and regularly updated data, the dashboard supports decision-making across OPERAS governance bodies, ensures transparency, and strengthens the infrastructure's strategic alignment with Open Science principles. Future plans include further automation of data sources, embedding the dashboard in the redesigned OPERAS website, and aligning the framework with the forthcoming Strategic Plan 2026–2028 and beyond.

¹ See Schulte, J., Caliman, L., & Păltineanu, S. (2023). Impact Monitoring Dashboard (OPERAS-PLUS Deliverable 8.2) (v1.0 Draft). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8289250>.

Contents

Contents	4
List of Abbreviations	5
Executive Summary	7
1. Introduction	9
2. Adaptations in Strategy and Methodology	11
3. Updated Key Performance Indicators and Impact	13
4. OPERAS Dashboard – Progress and Final Implementation	14
4.1 Dashboard Development & Structure	14
4.2 Performance Monitoring Dashboard	21
5. Impact Framework and Future Plans	26
Appendix 1 - Updated OPERAS RI Impact Indicators	28
Appendix 2 - PDF Download of the Impact Monitoring Dashboard	44

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List of Abbreviations

Abbreviation/Acronym	Definition
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AISBL	Association Internationale Sans But Lucratif (International non-profit association)
EC	European Commission
EDCH	European Diamond Capacity Hub
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
ESFRI	European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures
FTE	Full-Time Equivalent
FitSM	Federated IT Service Management
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
OA	Open Access
OAEBUDT	Open Access eBook Usage Data Trust
OCT	OPERAS Coordination Team
OER	Open Educational Resource
OPERAS	Open scholarly communication in the european research area for social sciences and humanities
PALOMERA	Policy Alignment of Open Access Monographs in the European Research Area
PDF	Portable Document Format
PRISM	Peer Review Information Service for

	Monographs
RDA	Research Data Alliance
RI	Research Infrastructure
RFO	Research Funding Organisation
RPO	Research Performing Organisation
SSH	Social Sciences and Humanities
VERA	Virtual Ecosystem for Research Activation
WP	Work Package

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Executive Summary

The deliverable presents the progress made since the release of Deliverable 8.2² in July 2023, focusing on transforming OPERAS' data monitoring from a manually maintained spreadsheet into a dynamic, integrated Impact Monitoring Dashboard in Google Looker Studio. This development responds to the need for better visualisation of trends over time, greater accessibility, and alignment with both performance monitoring and impact assessment principles set out by the ESFRI policy brief.

Key achievements include:

- **Strategic alignment:** Incorporating ESFRI's distinction between performance monitoring and impact assessment while recognising their interdependence in a research infrastructure.
- **Methodological refinement:** Updating KPIs to reflect evolving objectives, new activities, data availability, and stakeholder feedback; combining quantitative metrics with qualitative case studies to capture the multi-dimensional nature of impact.
- **Technical implementation:** Selecting Google Looker Studio for its cost-effectiveness, integration with existing Google sheets, and external data connectors (e.g., Matomo, social media channels).
- **Collaborative development & knowledge building:** Partnering with an external agency, Snoopmedia, for data structuring, connection setup, and dashboard design, ensuring usability for diverse audiences across OPERAS governance and operational teams.
- **Dashboard features:** Two sections—impact monitoring (public) and performance monitoring (restricted, with plans for broader access by the end of 2025)—with interactive visualisations, a glossary, and comment sections for context. Updates occur quarterly, where data cannot be retrieved automatically.

The deliverable also reports on updated KPIs across OPERAS' strategic pillars, including service uptake, communication reach, governance diversity, community training, and innovation outputs. Case studies illustrate qualitative dimensions of impact, from diversity in the Coordination Team to quality assessments of specific services.

Future steps involve embedding the dashboard into the relaunched OPERAS website (in the end of 2025), automating data integration to improve timeliness and accuracy, and adapting the impact assessment framework to the revised objectives of the

² See Schulte, J., Caliman, L., & Păltineanu, S. (2023). Impact Monitoring Dashboard (OPERAS-PLUS Deliverable 8.2) (v1.0 Draft). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8289250>.

Strategic Plan 2026–2028 and beyond. These efforts aim to ensure impact monitoring becomes a permanent, well-resourced, and strategically integrated activity within OPERAS.

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1. Introduction

As part of Work Package 8 (WP8) within the OPERAS-PLUS project, one of the key objectives was to develop tools that would not only communicate the achievements of OPERAS, but also enable the collection of crucial information needed to adapt and adjust the strategy and activities of the Research Infrastructure. These tools also serve to support OPERAS services (WP5), National Nodes (WP7), and the Innovation Lab (WP4).

This task makes it possible to assess the impact of the Research Infrastructure more precisely and to provide timely and accurate information to both the Executive Assembly and the General Assembly, but also for the OPERAS Coordination Team itself and all other OPERAS bodies. Such information is essential for guiding strategic evolution and enabling informed decision-making.

In July 2023, Deliverable 8.2 – the Impact Monitoring Dashboard – within the OPERAS-PLUS project was published. This marked a step forward in establishing a structured approach to collecting and analysing data about the OPERAS Research Infrastructure and its impact. However, the initial version of the dashboard focused heavily on quantitative data and lacked the ability to visualise growth and change over time. This capability is particularly important for various OPERAS bodies, including the OPERAS Coordination Team, as well as especially the communication and service teams, where information on indicators over a specific period could not be easily assessed, consolidated, or accessed through a single entry point by now.

2024 marked the year when the main focus was on collating usage statistics and Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) for each of the services, as well as analysis of usage behaviour for driving the next phase of development. Also, for the communication indicators, a more systematic approach was being conducted. The dashboard before was a simple Excel sheet collecting the data for every month manually. Some of the data is being collected, e.g. for the website and some indicators for the services via a Matomo³ Tool.

Since July 2024, and with a personal change in the leadership of Work Package 8, the focus has been on enhancing the dashboard to address these limitations and

³ [Matomo](https://matomo.org/), formerly known as Piwik, is a downloadable, [Free \(GPL licensed\)](https://matomo.org/) web analytics software platform. It provides detailed reports on your website and its visitors, including the search engines and keywords they used, the language they speak, which pages they like, the files they download and so much more. See: https://matomo.org/faq/new-to-piwik/faq_13/.

transforming it into a more suitable format. After considering different solutions and tools, this effort led to the implementation of the dashboard in Google Looker Studio⁴, providing a more accessible and insightful way for various OPERAS stakeholders to monitor progress, interpret results, and develop actionable recommendations based on data-driven insights.

In addition, the *OPERAS 2024 Annual Report*⁵ continued to gather and present case studies on various topics, further illustrating the impact of OPERAS through concrete examples and actions.

This deliverable is an additional textual explanation on the dashboard, explaining the progress made since the last deliverable 8.2 at the end of July 2023 and the final result, the **impact monitoring dashboard in Google Looker Studio, which can be accessed here:**

<https://lookerstudio.google.com/reporting/90b8234b-460b-4b7b-9974-232fec6953f4?hl=en>.

⁴ Looker Studio is a no-cost tool that turns data into informative, easy to read, easy to share, and fully customisable dashboards and reports. See: <https://cloud.google.com/looker/docs/studio>.

⁵ OPERAS, Töpfer, M., Caliman Fontes, L., & Semolič, N. (2025). Annual Report 2024. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15672537>.

2. Adaptations in Strategy and Methodology

At the end of June 2023 a ESFRI policy brief on *Assessment of Impact of Research Infrastructures*⁶ was published, outlining the importance of understanding the differences between performance monitoring, which ESFRI started implementing in 2022, and impact assessment (IA), ex-ante or ex-post, for research infrastructures (RIs). The policy brief provides recommendations to stakeholders, policymakers, funders, governments, RIs, ESFRI, and the EC.

The ESFRI policy brief was already recognised and cited within the last deliverable (8.2), but this was not reflected sufficiently. The distinction between Monitoring Performance and Impact Assessment mentioned in the policy brief was not clear enough in deliverable 8.2.

As highlighted in the ESFRI policy brief on *Assessment of Impact of Research Infrastructures* (p. 4), a clear conceptual distinction between performance monitoring and impact assessment is essential. While recognising this distinction is important, it is equally critical to consider both dimensions in conjunction, in order to gain a comprehensive understanding of a research infrastructure's trajectory and value. ESFRI further recommends that research infrastructures “[...] should reflect at an early stage on their performance and in what areas they would create impacts” (p. 5). In line with this recommendation, it has been — and remains — a strategic priority for OPERAS to engage with both levels of analysis, thereby enabling a more informed appraisal of its potential and actual contributions. Nevertheless, it should be acknowledged that the boundary between performance monitoring and impact assessment can at times be fluid, particularly in the case of research infrastructures at an early stage of their lifecycle, as is the case with OPERAS. Moreover, without recognising where a research infrastructure can generate impacts that fall outside its original vision, there is a risk of overlooking valuable and sometimes unexpected contributions and specific impact to the broader research ecosystem.

As suggested in the ESFRI policy brief on *Assessment of Impact of Research Infrastructures*, OPERAS worked extensively during the OPERAS-PLUS project towards a tailored approach to developing its own impact assessment methodology. As a

⁶ See: Kolar, J., Lutz, G., Angelieva, K., Angelis, J., Brecko, B., Chamberlain, M., Guittet, E., Karayannis, F., Plaskan, J., Ryan, M., Sobczak, D., & Wenzel-Constabel, P. (2023). ESFRI Policy Brief on Assessment of Impact of Research Infrastructures. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8091633>

relatively young research infrastructure — with the initial concept emerging in 2016–2017, formal design starting in 2017, and the first project (OPERAS-D) marking its launch — OPERAS has already built a solid database to support monitoring since the beginning. However, less than a decade of operation means that for certain indicators, particularly those relating to socio-economic impact, the available timeframe is still too short to yield robust measurements. Nevertheless, OPERAS is making steady progress towards a clearer understanding of where it generates impact and where it does not, enabling increasingly precise and evidence-based assessments in the future.

The **OPERAS customised impact assessment methodology** adopts a mixed-methods approach, integrating both quantitative and qualitative indicators across multiple areas directly linked to the infrastructure’s strategic objectives. **Quantitative indicators** include measurable outputs such as service uptake, platform and website usage statistics, publications enabled, and participation rates in training or dissemination activities. **Qualitative indicators** capture dimensions that are less readily quantifiable but equally relevant, such as community engagement, and perceived changes in research practices and landscapes. These mainly qualitative indicators are contextualised through a series of case studies that provide in-depth analyses of specific initiatives, illustrating how and where OPERAS generates impact. Some case studies are based on longitudinal data collected over several years, allowing for temporal comparisons and trend analysis, while others are exploratory, focusing on emerging areas of activity. This combined approach ensures that the assessment is not only aligned with OPERAS’ overarching mission but is also sensitive to the complex, multi-layered nature of research infrastructure impacts, including socio-economic, and scientific dimensions.

Additionally, as OPERAS is an evolving research infrastructure within the Social Sciences and Humanities landscape, performance and impact monitoring are naturally interconnected. At this stage, monitoring performance not only supports the identification and validation of additional growing impact but also provides valuable insights to guide strategic development and strengthen OPERAS’s role in the community. This perspective led to the decision to expand the dashboard with a performance monitoring component for internal governing bodies.

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3. Updated Key Performance Indicators and Impact

For the OPERAS Annual Report 2024, OPERAS made several adjustments to the original list of indicators described in Deliverable 8.2. These changes were necessary not only because certain indicators proved less suitable in practice, but also due to evolving priorities, refinements in OPERAS' strategic objectives, and the emergence of new activities requiring different measurement approaches. In some cases, relevant contextual factors have shifted since the original design, rendering specific indicators less meaningful or outdated. In others, data availability remains insufficient to produce reliable measurements, particularly for long-term or socio-economic impacts. Additionally, ongoing methodological improvements and feedback from stakeholders have prompted the inclusion of indicators better aligned with current operational realities and anticipated future developments.

The improved list was shown as follows in the appendix 1 of this deliverable, already in the OPERAS annual report 2024⁷, also with the specific data indicated and compared with those of 2023, demonstrating OPERAS' developing impact. The list and overview also present the case studies that have already been conducted, those that are planned, as well as those carried out during 2024 and before.

⁷ See OPERAS, Töpfer, M., Caliman Fontes, L., & Semolič, N. (2025). Annual Report 2024. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15672537>.

4. OPERAS Dashboard – Progress and Final Implementation

In this section, the structure of the monitoring dashboard and the development process leading to the final product will be described. The monitoring dashboard is designed to:

- Monitor and assess the impact of OPERAS
- Provide centralised access to data
- Offer data visualisation and analytical insights, including the possibility to explain underlying data
- Support decision-making processes
- Increase transparency.
- Additionally, enable both **performance** and **impact** monitoring, ensuring both are organised in relation to each other. A dedicated *Performance Monitoring Part* is for now only accessible for internal bodies, while the *Impact Monitoring* is already publicly available.

The final **Impact Monitoring Dashboard of OPERAS*** can be accessed here <https://lookerstudio.google.com/reporting/90b8234b-460b-4b7b-9974-232fec6953f4?hl=en> .

Please note that the dashboard may have current issues in Mozilla Firefox. **Google Chrome, Microsoft Edge, and Safari are recommended as browsers.*

4.1 Dashboard Development & Structure

Decision process for a dashboard tool

As part of the implementation of the OPERAS impact monitoring dashboard, **Google Looker Studio** was selected as the final tool for performance monitoring and impact assessment. This decision was preceded by an in-depth analysis of various dashboard solutions.

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Table 1: Analysis of 3 different dashboard tools for the OPERAS impact monitoring dashboard

Feature	Looker Studio	Tableau	Microsoft Power BI
How it looks	Highly configurable charts & tables, interactive dashboards; browser-based. Examples: Demo 1	Rich visualisations with advanced analytics, customizable dashboards. Examples: Showcase	Modern, interactive visuals with AI-driven insights. Examples: Gallery
Connectors	Free Google connectors (e.g., Google Ads, Analytics); 3rd party (e.g., Supermetrics, Matomo, YouTube); custom via Google Apps Script	Connects to almost any database; broad enterprise integrations	100+ connectors including Excel, SQL Server, Azure, Salesforce; custom connectors via API
Price Range	no-cost	Viewer: \$35/user/month; Explorer: \$70/user/month; Creator: \$115/user/month (annual)	Pro: \$10/user/month; Premium: \$20/user/month or capacity-based pricing
Sharing	Share via link; selective data hiding possible	Tableau Public allows sharing (data is public); private sharing via server/cloud	Share via Power BI Service, Teams, SharePoint; row-level security
Key Differences	Rapid creation of interactive reports; strong Google ecosystem integration	Enterprise-grade analytics with deep data exploration capabilities; training resources included	Strong Microsoft ecosystem integration, AI features, real-time dashboard updates

Platform Type	Cloud-based (browser)	Cloud or on-premises	Cloud-based with desktop authoring
Unique Strength	Free or low-cost entry, fast to set up	Robust analytics depth & enterprise scalability	Cost-effective, strong AI & Excel integration

In the initial phase, OPERAS used structured Google Sheets as its dashboard, accessible via the shared Confluence space, the internal collaboration platform. However, it soon became clear that there was a need for a more visual representation. Such a solution would also enable individuals who are either not particularly comfortable with numbers or have limited experience with data analysis to easily access and understand the valuable data. Given that all project data and supporting documents are stored on Google Drive, Google Looker Studio offers seamless integration with our existing ecosystem—particularly with Google Sheets and other Workspace tools—allowing for efficient, real-time data visualisation without the need for manual uploads. Furthermore, it is a no-cost tool that doesn’t apply any further financial commitments to OPERAS. Also, the external connectors to our tracking systems as Matomo or Social Media channels were available and at no-cost. Its intuitive interface enables the creation of dynamic, customisable dashboards that support both high-level summaries and detailed insights. Additionally, Looker Studio’s collaborative features align with our workflow needs, making it easy to share up-to-date reports via email or as PDF with all the different OPERAS bodies as well as stakeholders and ensure transparent, data-driven decision-making.

Evaluating Data and Structuring

After the decision to use Google Looker Studio as the tool for the final impact monitoring dashboard of OPERAS, the process began to evaluate the existing data, identify gaps, and determine where data needed to be better structured. This evaluation and improvement process took six months (September 2024 – February 2025) and included continuous assessment of whether Google Looker Studio remained the optimal choice. It also involved reviewing the previous Impact KPI list from Deliverable 8.2 and adapting it, resulting in the updated list presented in Appendix 1 of this deliverable.

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Knowledge, Structuring, and Data Connections

Since the necessary expertise within OPERAS was not fully available at the outset, knowledge sharing, the establishment of clear data structures, and the creation of reliable data connections were central to this phase. We also collaborated with Snoopmedia, a company from the industry, to organise various workshops and meetings and provide guidance on preparing data for connection to Google Looker Studio. This included advice on the structure of Google Sheets, setting up data connections with Google Sheets and external sources such as Matomo, and visualising data. As a result, a strong expertise and knowledge base was built within OPERAS. The kick-off took place on the 3rd of April 2025.

The process of setting up the dashboard encompassed:

1. Defining the Data and Info to show

- Determine what insights or KPIs the dashboard should provide, see page section 3 or appendix 1 of this deliverable
- Identifying the audiences: OPERAS coordination team, OPERAS bodies, the research community and stakeholders such as the EC and ministries, the public in general
- Decide on the metrics and dimensions needed: Therefore, for every indicator and the impact section, a dedicated Google Sheet was created, giving an overview of the specific metrics and additional info. See the example for some of the communication indicators below in figure 1.

2. Planning the Layout & Content

- Define a table of contents for the **Part 1 - Performance Monitoring** and **Part 2 - Impact Dashboard**, see *figure 1* below.

Contents

Part 1: Performance Monitoring Dashboard

1. Communication Indicators

- 1.1. [Website](#)
- 1.2. [Blog](#)
- 1.3. [Newsletter](#)
- 1.4. [Social Media](#)
- 1.5. [Publications](#)
- 1.6. [Events](#)

2. Community Indicators

- 2.1. [Members](#)
- 2.2. [National Nodes](#)

3. Service Indicators

- 3.1. [GoTriple](#)
- 3.2. [Metrics](#)
- 3.3. [VERA](#)
- 3.4. [Pathfinder](#)
- 3.5. [PRISM](#)
- 3.6. [Hypotheses](#)
- 3.7. [OPERAS ID](#)
- 3.8. [Messaging](#)
- 3.9. [FitSM Training](#)

4. Financial & Socio-economic Indicators

- 4.1. [Incomes and Expenses](#)
- 4.2. [OPERAS Coordination Team and OPERAS AISBL staff](#)

5. Governance & Management Indicators

- 5.1 [OPERAS bodies](#)

Figure 1: Contents for the Performance Monitoring Dashboard Part 1

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Contents

Part 2: Impact Monitoring Dashboard

[Objective 1. OPERAS as a pan-European, efficient organisation and highly representative of the SSH Open scholarly communication communities](#)

[Objective 2. The Diamond model supported as a major one in the scholarly communication ecosystem](#)

[Objective 3. OPERAS services published and integrated with EOSC and other marketplaces and communities](#)

[Objective 4. Clear set of well-defined and operational services](#)

[Objective 5. OPERAS members and communities are trained and knowledgeable in SSH FAIR and Open Science practices](#)

[Objective 6. OPERAS members are trained and knowledgeable in SSH open science service delivery](#)

[Objective 7. OPERAS as a trusted advisor for national and European OS strategies](#)

[Objective 8. Academic books are included in the Open Science policies](#)

[Objective 9. Setting up a pan-European OPERAS innovation lab](#)

Figure 2: Contents for the Impact Monitoring Dashboard Part 2

- Sketch a dashboard wireframe, see *figure 3* below.
- Decide on chart types: tables, line charts, bar charts, pie charts, etc., see also the *figure 3* below.

Communication Indicators	Info: Data since 2021	Communication Indicators					
Page 1	Website www.operas-eu.org				Blog https://operas.hypotheses.org/		
KPI/Metric	#unique visitors website (Target: more than 9.600 per year)	#unique visits (below increase in percent to previous year)	#3 most visited webpages last full year	#3 channels of website	# unique visitors Blog (Target: >2.500/month)	#blog posts (Target: >15/year)	#page visits
Diagram Type	total for the last full year (below increase to previous year)	total for the last full year (below increase in percent to previous year)	table	table	total for the last full year+country map	total for the last full year	total for the last full year
Diagram Type 2	line diagram of unique visitors and unique visits together since 2021, including already 2025				line diagram over the years all together		
Diagram Type 3	country map						
Data Source	Matomo Huma-Num	Matomo Huma-Num	Matomo Huma-Num	Matomo Huma-Num	Matomo in hypotheses (B)	Communication Indicators	Matomo in hypotheses

Figure 3: Example for the communication indicators and the structuration of the data for the dashboard

3. Collecting and Connecting Data

- Connect to data sources: Matomo, Google Sheets, YouTube
- Ensure data quality and structure are sufficient for reporting

4. Building the Dashboard

- Create a report in Looker Studio
- Customising the design to the OPERAS visual corporate identity
- Add charts, tables, and visual components
- Configure dimensions, metrics, filters, and segments

6. Review and Test

- Check for accuracy of metrics + review by the responsible people for collecting the data or supervising it
- Ensure interactivity works properly
- Validate data refresh schedules if using live data sources - the update rhythm of the dashboard was set to every 3 months for OPERAS (last update 30th of June 2025, next update 30th of September)

Presentation of the Structure & Access

With the OPERAS-PLUS project, OPERAS has taken a significant first step toward integrating data into the decision-making processes of its various governance bodies through the establishment of the final dashboard. The rollout began with smaller groups, including the Communication Team, the Services Team, and the OPERAS Coordination Team, and is being extended to the Executive Assembly. In the coming

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months, the dashboard will also be presented to the Science and Technology Board, the Scientific Advisory Committee, the General Assembly, the Board of Governing Representatives, and the Assembly of the Commons.

The responsible personnel were involved in selecting the data and reviewing the dashboard's presentation multiple times between May and August (see table in D8.2, page 38). The OPERAS Coordination Team and the Executive Assembly also conducted comprehensive reviews.

As previously mentioned, ensuring a strong connection between performance monitoring and impact monitoring was essential. For this reason, the dashboard has been structured into two distinct parts. While the Executive Assembly of OPERAS has not yet made a final decision—expected in September—the performance monitoring section is currently accessible only to the OPERAS Coordination Team and the Executive Assembly. Additional OPERAS bodies will gain access during Q3 2025, and public access is also planned. The impact monitoring section, by contrast, is already publicly accessible.

The implementation of this dashboard is guided by the principle highlighted in the ESFRI policy brief that impact assessment can “contribute to the strategic planning of an RI, reflecting on internal resource allocation and leading to constant improvement and focusing of services according to the needs of users and other stakeholders” (p. 5). It also fosters accountability and transparency, providing legitimacy, visibility, and value to the infrastructure.

Therefore, OPERAS aims to actively contribute to this process and ensure transparency with both the research community and the general public, as transparency is a core principle of Open Science and open scholarly communication.

In parallel, the OPERAS website is being redesigned and is scheduled for relaunch in late 2025. The renewed website will feature the embedded impact monitoring dashboard, which will be available at operas-eu.org/impact (accessible from the end of 2025).

4.2 Performance Monitoring Dashboard

At present, access to the performance monitoring section of the dashboard is controlled via Google email authentication and is currently restricted to the OPERAS Coordination Team and the Executive Assembly. This ensures secure handling of

sensitive operational data until the Executive Assembly approves it (a decision is expected for September). It is planned to make this part of the dashboard also accessible to everyone.

The structure of this Performance Monitoring section follows the five core indicator categories of OPERAS:

- Communication Indicators,
- Service Indicators,
- Community Indicators,
- Governance and Management Indicators,
- and Financial and Socio-Economic Indicators.

Each dashboard page includes a dedicated Glossary and a comment section at the bottom, enabling users to access clear definitions of all terms and methodologies used, as well as contextual notes on data interpretation. This approach supports both internal knowledge transfer and transparency, ensuring that all authorised users can interpret the data accurately and consistently. Different types of diagrams were used, and some pages are interactive, allowing users to access data for a specific time frame. Below you can find a preview of some pages of the communication indicators within the performance monitoring part of the dashboard.

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01.01.2025 - 24.08.2025

Key performance indicators

Total visits
21.860

Visits in total previous year (Target per year: 9.600)
38.320
2024

Daily visits

Traffic sources: Channels

Most visited pages

Page URL	Pageviews
1. /	7.530
2. /news-and-events/calendar-2/action~agenda/page_offset~-1/ - Others	2.524
3. /projects/palomera/	2.421
4. /news-and-events/calendar-2/public-launch-almasi-project-and-european-di...	1.760
5. /about/	1.319
6. /about/operas-in-a-nutshell/	1.223
7. /news-and-events/calendar-2/action~agenda/ - Others	1.075
8. /about/governance-schema/members/	1.026
9. /about/governance-schema/coordination-team/	977
10. /special-interest-group-living-book/diamond-open-access-in-scholarly-publis...	709
11. /operas-national-nodes/	708
12. /projects/palomera/results/recommendations-for-open-access-academic-b...	594
13. /about/want-to-know-more/want-to-join-operas/	551
14. /services/	547
15. /projects/graphia/	494
16. /services/discovery-service-triple/	441
17. /calls-and-job-opportunities/	429
18. /services/metrics-service/	415
19. /finance-officer-ref-202501-fo/	390
20. /projects/operas-plus/	366

1 - 20 / 3988

Visits by country

Country	Visits
1. Germany	6.781
2. United States	1.949
3. France	1.691
4. Slovenia	1.470
5. United Kingdom	1.088
6. Italy	1.025
7. Spain	782
8. Belgium	639
9. Poland	492
10. Portugal	454
11. Netherlands	446
12. China	439
13. Greece	340
14. Canada	305
15. Croatia	276
16. Singapore	268
17. Switzerland	240
18. Hong Kong SAR China	219
19. Finland	218
20. Russia	198

1 - 20 / 131

Glossary

KPI (Key Performance Indicator): A specific, measurable value used to assess progress toward defined goals within the research infrastructure.

Visit = refers to one individual session during which a user accesses and interacts with a website. It starts when the user enters the site and ends after a certain period of inactivity or when the user leaves the site. One person can have multiple visits.

= Static KPI / This KPI does not change when a different time period is selected.

Comments

Note on displayed data: This page is interactive. When you select a time period using the bar at the top left, all metrics on the page will update accordingly – except for the static number in the top right. Data is available starting from June 3, 2020 for the OPERAS website. If you select a date before this, the chosen time period will not apply. All numbers reflect only the selected time period.

Note on target per year: This indicator was defined at the beginning of the OPERAS-PLUS project in September 2022 and has been significantly exceeded. The target will be adjusted soon.

Key performance indicators

Total Blog posts
128
since 2021

Blog posts in total previous year (Target per year: 15)
31
2024

Published blog posts & page visits

Visits by country (Top 5)

2022

2023

2024

2025

Glossary

KPI (Key Performance Indicator): A specific, measurable value used to assess progress toward defined goals within the research infrastructure.

Comments

Hypotheses: is one of the services in the OPERAS service catalogue and is provided by OpenEdition. OPERAS runs a blog on Hypotheses featuring news items and blog series on various topics.

Note on target per year: This indicator was defined at the beginning of the OPERAS-PLUS project in September 2022 and has been significantly exceeded. The target will be adjusted soon.

Data page visits: The data collection for page visits began in July 2022, as a different tracking tool was used prior to that date.

Key performance indicators

Total social media followers
6.759

Total social media followers prev. year
5.515
2024

Total Posts on Social Media
2.201
since 2022

Posts on Social Media 2024
903
2024

Followers by platform

Glossary

KPI (Key Performance Indicator): A specific, measurable value used to assess progress toward defined goals within the research infrastructure.

Comments

X channel: OPERAS discontinued its presence on Platform X as of January 24, 2025, due to the platform's shift away from values aligned with OPERAS' commitment to fostering trust, openness, and transparency in our work and for research, see also <https://operas.hypotheses.org/8559>.

Bluesky channel: OPERAS opened in January 2025 a Bluesky channel.

YouTube channel: OPERAS opened its YouTube channel only in November 2021.

5. Impact Framework and Future Plans

The current OPERAS impact assessment framework is grounded in the four pillars of the Research Infrastructure and their associated objectives, as defined in the Strategic Plan 2023–2025. However, during the Executive Assembly meeting in Paris in early May 2025, new discussions on the Strategic Plan 2026–2028 led to a major strategic shift. It was decided not to continue with the existing objectives linked to the four pillars, and in several cases, the objectives themselves were revised — in some instances substantially.

Therefore, the impact monitoring framework of OPERAS should be adapted at the end of 2025, establishing a framework with long-term consistency and more aligned with the suggestions of the ESFRI policy brief, see the overview below:

Figure 1. An example of impacts coming out from the communication and outreach activities.

Source: RI-PATHS project

Figure 4: Sobczak, D., & Wenzel-Constabel, P. (2023). *ESFRI Policy Brief on Assessment of Impact of Research Infrastructures*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8091633>, page 10.

During the upcoming months, the dashboard will be presented to the different OPERAS governing bodies, ensuring that they can make full use of the dashboard for informed decision-making, while also fostering the generation of new initiatives and approaches to maximise OPERAS' impact. Workshops are planned for this activity. The dashboard will be subject to continuous improvement, with particular attention to enhancing data integration. In the current setup, several data sources are manually updated via Google Sheets; however, plans are in place to establish direct, automated connections between these sources and the dashboard. Such automation will not only reduce the risk of human error but also improve data timeliness, reliability, and efficiency as well as interactivity of the dashboard in line with best practices for research

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infrastructure monitoring systems. While the required programming and system integration entail a considerable development effort, implementation is foreseen as part of the dashboard's next enhancement phase.

As highlighted in the ESFRI policy brief (p. 6), integrating an impact analysis framework into the governance system of a Research Infrastructure is essential for consistently tracking its impacts over time and capturing their evolution. To achieve this, impact assessment must become a permanent activity, supported by dedicated human and financial resources. This ongoing maintenance is critical to ensuring the reliability, continuity, and usability of the OPERAS impact framework.

Appendix 1 - Updated OPERAS RI Impact Indicators

Pillar: Redesigning Ecosystem

Objective 1. OPERAS as a pan-European, efficient organisation and highly representative of the SSH Open scholarly communication communities

Area	Indicator	2023	2024	In total
Growth (Size, Outreach)	# New ordinary members (per country, European and non-European)	5 <i>(Cyprus 1, France 2, Spain 1, UK 1)</i>	7 <i>(Denmark 1, France 1, Germany 1, Poland 2, UK 2)</i>	All ordinary members: 52
	# New core members	3 <i>(Spain, Finland, Norway)</i>	0	All core members: 13
	# New supporting members	1 <i>(France)</i>	0	All supporting members: 4
	# Private organisations within OPERAS members	5	5	5
Public awareness &	# Visits on the OPERAS	27,811	38,320 <i>(increase of</i>	

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Outreach ⁸	website		37,8%)	
	# Followers on OPERAS Social media channels	4,533	5,515 <i>(increase of 21,66 %)</i>	
	# Social Media posts on all OPERAS social media channels	587	903 <i>(increase of 53,84%)</i>	
	# Publications on Zenodo	133	78	436
	# Other Publications	1	2	
	# Events of OPERAS <i>(counting training as separate)</i>	47	45	
	# Project related events	126	105	
	# People reached and engaged in	1294	839	

⁸ Most indicators are measured without taking into account the project activities of which OPERAS is a part, unless this is clearly indicated. The 2023 data has been updated accordingly.

	OPERAS events			
	# People reached and engaged in project related events	6000	7140	
	# Hours of OPERAS events	53	70	
Collaborations/ Building a European Network	Qualitative Use case: collaboration in a long-term perspective	<i>Long-term evaluation to be conducted once collaboration completes minimum 10 years.</i>		
Service Providers	# Members in the Services and Technologies Board	8 organisations	10 organisations (24 persons)	
	# Agreements with Service Providers	1	4	4
	# Private organisations / SMEs providing service	4	5	5

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	components for OPERAS			
Financial and Economic	FTE (full-time-equivalent) employees (AISBL)	10.8 FTE	12.9 FTE	
	# country of work/ number of nationalities of OPERAS AISBL staff	<p>8 countries (Belgium, France, Germany, Greece, Italy, Netherlands, Portugal, Switzerland)/</p> <p>11 Nationalities (Belarusian, Belgian, Brazilian, Croatian, French, German, Greek, Italian, Portuguese, Taiwanese, US-American)</p>	<p>8 countries (Belgium, France, Germany, Greece, Italy, Netherlands, Portugal, Switzerland)/</p> <p>12 Nationalities (Belarusian, Belgian, Brazilian, Croatian, French, German, Greek, Italian, Portuguese, Russian, Taiwanese, US-American)</p>	

	# Number of new jobs at each level - senior and junior (AISBL)	5 <i>senior</i>	2 senior	
	Case study: Diversity of people and professional background (examples)	Case Study: Leveraging Diversity for a Stronger European Research Infrastructure: The Case of the OPERAS coordination team,		

Case Study: Leveraging Diversity for a Stronger European Research Infrastructure: The Case of the OPERAS coordination team

OPERAS, a key European research infrastructure (RI) for open scholarly communication in the Social Sciences and Humanities, stands as a model for diversity and inclusivity. This is reflected not only in its ability to bring together various stakeholders, members, and research communities in open scholarly communication within the social sciences and humanities (SSH) and beyond, but also in the OPERAS Coordination Team (OCT), which includes OPERAS AISBL staff.

As in our Code of Conduct⁹, “We support diversity in all dimensions.” This principle applies to every activity we undertake. The tangible impact of the diverse composition of the OPERAS coordination team in its operational effectiveness, stakeholder engagement, and capacity to develop and deliver innovative solutions.

The OPERAS coordination team is the central hub of OPERAS comprising by the end of 2024 of 20 persons: 14 hired by OPERAS AISBL and 6 persons working for 4 different (core) members of OPERAS (OpenEdition - France, University of Coimbra - Portugal, Max Weber Stiftung - Germany, University of Zadar - Croatia). This collaboration of OPERAS AISBL staff and staff from OPERAS member institutions demonstrates our distributed approach in community management. OPERAS is committed to diversity of interpretation and believes that many ways can lead to our common goal.

⁹ See the code of conduct, <https://operas-eu.org/about/governance-schema/coordination-team/how-we-work/>

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Within the OPERAS coordination team, individuals from a wide range of nationalities, cultural, linguistic, disciplinary and professional backgrounds can be found. Specifically in 2024, the team:

- consists of people from Asia (1), Europe (16), North (1) and South America (3) creating a dynamic and intercultural environment.
- average age range: 26 - 35 = 5%; 36 - 45 = 55%, 46 - 55 = 35%
- Gender: Female 66,67% , Male 33,33%
- Has a professional background that ranges from industry (business, film, marketing) to scholarly based professions including those related to research, library work and publishing.
- 12 Nationalities (Belarusian, Belgian, Brazilian, Croatian, French, German, Greek, Italian, Portuguese, Russian, Taiwanese, US-American)
- 57,14 % of the staff work from another country than their first nationality, working in 8 European countries.

The variety of personal and professional backgrounds in the OPERAS coordination team leads to:

- **A centre of various competencies:**

Cloud of competencies from the OPERAS coordination team, December 2024

- **Enhanced multicultural collaboration:**

The diversity of nationalities and cultural perspectives has led to the adoption of best practices in intercultural communication and project management, fostering collaboration across borders and disciplines.

- Innovation and idea hub through diverse perspectives:**
 The interplay of different professional and academic backgrounds and experiences enhances creativity and problem-solving, leading to innovative approaches to open scholarly communication in SSH.
- Alignment with European Commission priorities:**
 OPERAS AISBL's diversity directly supports European values and policy priorities, including the European Research Area's emphasis on gender equality, diversity, and inclusiveness in research. It also contributes to the European Commission's goals for international cooperation in research and innovation.

An intercultural environment strengthens team competencies but also requires continuous training. A dedicated training on intercultural communication and organisation in December 2024 supported the capacity-building and will lead to further organisational structure changes in 2025 within the OPERAS coordination team.

Beyond the OPERAS coordination team, the research infrastructure is also further strengthening diversity in its governance to better reflect the full spectrum of the SSH community. This is already visible in the composition of OPERAS' governance bodies.

With a team composed of individuals from different backgrounds, professions and perspectives, OPERAS is better positioned to meet the needs of Europe's diverse research communities and to foster a more inclusive, innovative, and impactful European Research Area.

Pillar: Supporting bibliodiversity

Objective 2. The Diamond model supported as a major one in the scholarly communication ecosystem

Area	Indicator	2024*
Community Building	# Institutional publishers using the European Diamond Capacity Hub	
Capacity Hub	# Number of training events offered by	

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	European Diamond Capacity Hub	
	# Diamond journals in the Diamond Discovery Hub database	

**Given the recent launch of the European Diamond Capacity Hub in January 2025, it is currently not possible to track or report the previously mentioned indicators within this annual report. Data collection for these indicators will start during 2025 and will be presented in future reports. Likewise, the Diamond Discovery Hub database, which is being developed within the CRAFT-OA project, will only be launched in June 2025, meaning those indicators are also not yet available. Nevertheless, the early impact of these initiatives is already visible: Diamond is playing a major role within national communities, with several countries, including Finland, Norway, Sweden, Germany, and Italy, actively preparing to set up their own national Diamond Hubs. This highlights the growing momentum and relevance of Diamond initiatives across Europe.*

Pillar: Empowering Community

Objective 3. OPERAS services published and integrated with EOSC and other marketplaces and communities

Area	Indicator	2023	2024	In total
Uptake of OPERAS services ¹⁰	# Visits of each OPERAS managed service	GoTriple 15,425	GoTriple 192,700 VERA 1,886 Metrics 240 Pathfinder 653 ¹¹	

¹⁰ The OPERAS services VERA, Metrics and Pathfinder were in Beta version in 2023, therefore no data is available for that year.

¹¹ Data collected only from March 2024.

	<p># Top 3 European countries in which the services are most used</p>	<p>GoTriple <i>Italy, Germany, France</i></p>	<p>GoTriple Germany, France, UK VERA France, Italy, UK Metrics UK, Spain, Germany Pathfinder Italy, France, UK</p>	
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OPERAS has **6** services in the OPERAS service catalogue and **9** in the OPERAS service portfolio. (Status May 2025)

- **GoTriple**, a discovery platform for Social Sciences and Humanities in multiple languages, provides access to over **17,5 million documents by the end of 2024 from more than 1,400 data sources (an increase of 2,5 million documents compared to the previous year)**.
- **Hypotheses**, a dedicated service fostering research dialogues and impact through academic blogging, draws approximately **1 million unique visitors** per month, hosts around **5,000 active blogs**, and engages almost **22,000 active accounts (around 2,000 more accounts than in the previous year)**.
- **VERA**, activating participatory research in Citizen Science, supports **more than 100 projects**.
- **PRISM**, a tool for increasing transparency about peer review processes for monographs, hosts **approximately 6,000 titles and connects 20 publishers**.
- **Pathfinder**, a service aimed at finding editorial services for academic publishing, collaborates with **7 service providers (3 more than in the previous year)** to offer **34 options (7 more than in the previous year)**.
- **Metrics**, a service measuring usage and impact of Open Access content, engages with **82 publishers (33 more than in the previous year)** and about **8,300 books tracked (5,000 more than in the previous year)**, complemented by the installation of around **40 widgets** to enhance user interaction and accessibility.

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- Significant progress includes the operationalisation of the **OPERAS ID (1,148 registered users by the end of 2024)**, which simplifies user access across all OPERAS services and currently integrates Google, ORCID and EGI Check-in, others in the development pipeline, and the **FitSM training** that enhances service management capabilities within the community.

These developments underscore OPERAS' commitment to fostering an integrated and efficient research infrastructure.

Pillar: Fostering quality

Objective 4. Clear set of well-defined and operational services

Area	Indicator	2023	2024	In total
Services	# OPERAS Services in the Services Portfolio	9	9	9
	# OPERAS Services in Evaluation		2	
Business models for Services	% Availability/ Reliability of the service	<i>This indicator can only be measured in the future to assess the capability.</i>		
	% Services with a clear defined business model	<i>Further evaluation is required for this indicator as all the services are self-funded currently.</i>		
FitSM	# Personal Certifications		57 directly (facilitated 300+)	

			<i>through our facilitated trainer network)¹²</i>	
	Use case: services and the clear-defined business models	<i>Further evaluation is required for this indicator as all the services are self-funded currently.</i>		
	Case study: Quality of the OPERAS services	Case study: Elaborating the quality of OPERAS services: GoTriple and the ATRIUM Researcher Forum <i>(see below this table)</i>		

Case study: Assessing the quality of OPERAS services: GoTriple and the ATRIUM Researcher Forum

One of the ways in which a Research Infrastructure can measure and improve the quality of its services is a Researcher Forum. In this context, the OPERAS discovery service *GoTriple* was the target of one of these events, organised by the ATRIUM project (Advancing Frontier Research in the Arts and Humanities). The ATRIUM Researcher Forum on GoTriple was realised in October 2024 and its main goal was to gather feedback from users and experts about GoTriple to identify the platform’s strengths and areas for improvement.

Twelve researchers from Poland took part in the event, divided into two groups: new users and experts. The new users group participated in a usability test in which they performed tasks on the GoTriple platform while verbalising their thoughts and challenges encountered. They also participated in a follow-up group discussion about their experience with the platform during the test. The experts group engaged in a focus group to evaluate key features of GoTriple and in a panel to discuss potential development directions for the platform.

Together, the organiser of the event and the GoTriple team identified some key results, both in the platform strengths and challenges. Among the strengths, the platform was

¹² Thanks to the OPERAS training initiatives and the resources accredited by APMG.

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found to be intuitive, user-friendly with an easy navigation, having useful filtering and knowledge maps/streamgraphs, and a promising chatbot. Challenges include limitation of literature representation in given areas, needing better integration with external tools, an improvement of the search in languages other than English and a potential to expand extra tools.

The first Researcher Forum will be followed by a second one, to be realised in 2025. And the results are already being put into practice, with the GoTriple team using the feedback to improve the platform continuously, and leveraging the lessons learned also in following projects such as FASCA, GRAPHIA and LUMEN.

Read more about it: <https://atrium-research.eu/news/atrium-first-researcher-forum/>

Pillar: Empowering community

Objective 5. OPERAS members and communities are trained and knowledgeable in SSH FAIR and Open Science practices

Area	Indicator	2023 ¹³	2024	In total since 2024
Training	# Training events of OPERAS National Nodes		2 (Italy) 1 (Croatia)	3
	# Participants attending training events		110	110
	Use case: Uptake of FAIR principles	<i>Data collection for this indicator is currently not feasible and requires further evaluation</i>		

Pillar: Fostering Quality

Objective 6. OPERAS members are trained and knowledgeable in SSH open science service delivery

¹³ The data of the National Nodes have been collected since 2024, as a result of the Roadmap for the OPERAS National Nodes.

Area	Indicator	2023	2024	In total
Service delivery	# Training events (FitSM)	6	1	7
	# Training participants (FitSM)	37	8	45

Pillar: Redesigning Ecosystem

Objective: 7. OPERAS as a trusted advisor for national and European OS strategies

Area	Indicator	2023	2024	In total
Scientific advisor and engagement with policymakers	Case study: Example of consultation	Case study: The PALOMERA validation process (see below this table)		
	# Policy briefs		1	1
	Case study: Notable changes in policy decisions	<i>The impact of OPERAS activities on notable changes in policy decisions cannot be validated enough at the moment. But it is under constant evaluation and will be conducted within the next 2-3 years.</i>		
	Case study: OPERAS impactful publications	<i>See Key Publications of 2024 in the appendix 2 of this annual report</i>		

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Engagement with key initiatives	# & Case study: Boards and task forces of which OPERAS is a member	5 (CoARA, EOSC, RDA working group, SSHOC, OAEBUDT)	7 (CoARA, EASSH, EDCH, EOSC, RDA working group, SSHOC, OAEBUDT)	7
Case study: OPERAS already conducted a “USE CASE: Boards and task forces of which OPERAS is a member” for the annual report 2023, see: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11349719 (page 67) .				

Case study: The PALOMERA validation process

The PALOMERA (Policy Alignment of Open Access Monographs in the European Research Area) project, of which OPERAS is a coordinator, demonstrates a sophisticated approach to stakeholder consultation through its structured validation exercises. As documented in Deliverable 5.3¹⁴, these exercises represent a methodical process for ensuring that key project outputs receive proper assessment from diverse stakeholders across the European Research Area.

PALOMERA distinguished validation from other engagement activities by focusing on obtaining collective assessment from stakeholders regarding the validity of project outputs. The project implemented three distinct validation exercises, each tailored to a specific Key Exploitable Result (KER):

- Knowledge Base Validation (January 2024): This two-part exercise involved 34 participants representing 17 countries and all relevant stakeholder types (RFOs, RPOs, researchers, policymakers, publishers, libraries). The process included initial presentation, feedback collection via Google Forms, and focused breakout discussions to assess the completeness of the Knowledge Base and explore

¹⁴ Available in: <https://zenodo.org/records/14265343>. Last accessed on May 28, 2025.

potential use cases.

- Analysis Validation (June 2024): Taking the form of scholarly peer review, this in-person exercise brought together three expert reviewers from different geographical locations (US, UK, France) with diverse backgrounds to evaluate the analysis of OA book policies using the PESTLE framework.
- Recommendations Validation (September 2024): This five-step process included initial feedback gathering, presentation of draft recommendations, structured feedback collection, breakout discussions by stakeholder type, and final refinement. The exercise engaged 28 participants from 14 countries.

The validation exercises deliberately involved all stakeholder types identified in the project's Grant Agreement, including research funders, research institutions, researchers, policymakers, publishers, and libraries. This comprehensive approach ensured that the project's outputs would be judged valid by those who would ultimately implement or be affected by OA book policies.

This case from the PALOMERA project illustrates how structured validation exercises can serve as an effective consultation mechanism within research infrastructure projects. Co-coordinated by OPERAS, the project is an example of how the infrastructure positions itself as an advisor for Open Science and Open Scholarly Communication.

Pillar: Supporting Bibliodiversity

Objective O8. Academic books are included in the Open Science policies

Area	Indicator	2023	2024	In total
A set of recommendations and resources provided to support institutional	# Recommendations		43 (single recommendations)	
	Case study: Examples on	Case study: OPERAS already conducted a "USE CASE: How		

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strategies and funder policies for open access books	how recommendations are used	recommendations are used?” for the annual report 2023, see on page 66: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11349719 .
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Pillar: Empowering Community

Objective O9. Setting up a pan-European OPERAS innovation lab

Area	Indicator	2023	2024	In total
Innovation	# of calls run through the innovation lab	0	2	2
	# of blog posts on the observatory	6	9	15
	# of new services proposed to the OPERAS service portfolio	0	1	1
	# of new pilot proposals submitted	0	3	3
	# of case studies + case study	0	4	4
	Case study: All case studies of the innovation lab can be found here: https://lab.operas-eu.org/category/observatory/innovation-lab-case-study/ .			

Appendix 2 - PDF Download of the Impact Monitoring Dashboard

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OPERAS

open scholarly communication in the european
research area for social sciences and humanities

Impact Monitoring Dashboard

Contents

Part 2: Impact Monitoring Dashboard

[Objective 1. OPERAS as a pan-European, efficient organisation and highly representative of the SSH Open scholarly communication communities](#)

[Objective 2. The Diamond model supported as a major one in the scholarly communication ecosystem](#)

[Objective 3. OPERAS services published and integrated with EOSC and other marketplaces and communities](#)

[Objective 4. Clear set of well-defined and operational services](#)

[Objective 5. OPERAS members and communities are trained and knowledgeable in SSH FAIR and Open Science practices](#)

[Objective 6. OPERAS members are trained and knowledgeable in SSH open science service delivery](#)

[Objective 7. OPERAS as a trusted advisor for national and European OS strategies](#)

[Objective 8. Academic books are included in the Open Science policies](#)

[Objective 9. Setting up a pan-European OPERAS innovation lab](#)

About the Impact Monitoring Dashboard

Impact Monitoring Framework

In 2023, OPERAS started to develop a comprehensive monitoring framework to evaluate the impact of the Research Infrastructure. This framework provides a structured approach to oversee OPERAS activities and supports strategic decision-making through a set of clearly defined Key Performance Indicators (KPIs). These KPIs are aligned with OPERAS' mission, pillars and current objectives, and they help demonstrate its contribution to society, the economy, innovation, and policy development.

During 2024, OPERAS continued its work on the monitoring framework, a structured data collection, and a way to present visually its impact and additionally also performance monitoring. At the end of August 2025 (as part of the OPERAS-PLUS project), OPERAS launched this dedicated online dashboard offering an accessible, transparent and interactive overview of its performance monitoring (Part 1 - internally) and impact monitoring (Part 2 - publicly) across these indicators. This marks an important step in operationalising the framework and sharing progress with stakeholders and the broader research community. As of now, the performance monitoring section is only visible to OPERAS bodies, while the impact section is accessible to the entire community and the general public.

Instructions for the Usage of the Dashboard

Some pages of this report are interactive, meaning that data is automatically retrieved from its original sources in real time. This may occasionally result in longer loading times.

The data in this dashboard is updated quarterly. The most recent update was **on 30 June 2025**, and the next scheduled update **will be on 30 September 2025**.

You can interact with filters, date selectors, and other controls where available to explore specific data segments or time periods. Hover over charts for additional insights or explanations.

On each page of the performance monitoring part, you will also find additional support in the footer, including a glossary and comments section. In the impact monitoring section, you will find a dedicated area titled "Information on reading the Impact" to help you better understand the data and provide further context.

Objective 1. OPERAS as a pan-European, efficient organisation and highly representative of the SSH Open scholarly communication communities

Growth (Size and Outreach)

Notes

New ordinary members: 2023 from Cyprus 1, France 2, Spain 1, UK 1; 2024 from Denmark 1, France 1, Germany 1, Poland 2, UK 2; 2025 from Croatia 1, France 1

New core members: 2023 from Spain 1, Finland 1, Norway 1

New supporting members: 2023 from France 1

Public awareness & outreach

Information on reading the impact

Monitoring Framework: OPERAS has established a monitoring framework within the OPERAS-PLUS project, aligned with its objectives for 2023–2025. The framework is under constant development and uses 2023 as its starting point, as data from earlier periods is incomplete. The monitoring of impact includes various indicators, as well as case studies and use cases that have been conducted or are planned. See also: D8.2: <https://zenodo.org/records/8289250> and D8.7: <https://zenodo.org/records/1693374444> of OPERAS-PLUS.

Data 2025: The data is based on the last update as of June 30th, 2025. For some indicators, data is not yet available. The dashboard is continuously being updated. The next update is scheduled for September 30th, 2025.

Public awareness & outreach

Collaborations/Building a European Network

Qualitative Use case: collaboration in a long-term perspective

Long-term evaluation to be conducted once collaboration completes minimum 10 years.

Information on reading the impact

Monitoring Framework: OPERAS has established a monitoring framework within the OPERAS-PLUS project, aligned with its objectives for 2023–2025. The framework is under constant development and uses 2023 as its starting point, as data from earlier periods is incomplete. The monitoring of impact includes various indicators, as well as case studies and use cases that have been conducted or are planned. See also: D8.2: <https://zenodo.org/records/8289250> and D8.7: <https://zenodo.org/records/1693374444> of OPERAS-PLUS.

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Service providers

Financial & economic

Notes

Countries of work: Belgium, France, Germany, Greece, Italy, Netherlands, Portugal, Switzerland

Nationalities: 2023 Belarusian, Belgian, Brazilian, Croatian, French, German, Greek, Italian, Portuguese, Taiwanese, US-American + 2024 Russian

Case study: Diversity of people and professional background (examples)

Case study: Leveraging Diversity for a Stronger European Research Infrastructure: The Case of the OPERAS coordination team. <https://zenodo.org/records/15672537> (page 80 - 82)

Information on reading the impact

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Objective 2. The Diamond model supported as a major one in the scholarly communication ecosystem

Community building (no data available yet)*

Capacity hub (no data available yet)*

* Given the recent launch of the European Diamond Capacity Hub in January 2025, it is currently not possible to track or report the previously mentioned indicators. Data collection for these indicators will start during 2025 and will be presented in the upcoming months. Likewise, the Diamond Discovery Hub database, which is being developed within the CRAFT-OA project, was launched in the end of June 2025, meaning those indicators are also not yet available. Nevertheless, the early impact of these initiatives is already visible: Diamond is playing a major role within national communities, with several countries, including Finland, Norway, Sweden, Germany, and Italy, actively preparing to set up their own national Diamond Hubs. This highlights the growing momentum and relevance of Diamond initiatives across Europe

Information on reading the impact

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Objective 3. OPERAS services published and integrated with EOSC and other marketplaces and communities

Uptake of OPERAS services

Since Q1 2023 in Production

Since Q4 2023 in Production

Since Q4 2023 in Production

Since Q3 2025 in Production

Service in comparison

Due to the significantly higher number of hits on GoTriple and the resulting overrepresentation, this has been moved to a separate chart

Information on reading the impact

In this chart only the OPERAS managed services are shown. The OPERAS services VERA, Metrics and Pathfinder were in Beta version in 2023, therefore no data is available for that year.

Pathfinder: Data collected only from March 2024.

Top 3 European countries in which the services are most used

2023
GoTriple: Italy, Germany, France

2024
GoTriple: Germany, France, UK
VERA: France, Italy, UK
Metrics: UK, Spain, Germany
Pathfinder: Italy, France, UK

Objective 4. Clear set of well-defined and operational services

Services

Business models for Services

Year	% Availability/ Reliability of the service	% Services with a clear defined business model
1. 2023	0 %	0 %
2. 2024	0 %	0 %
3. 2025	0 %	0 %

1 - 3 / 3 < >

Notes

% Availability/ Reliability of the service: This indicator can only be measured in the future to assess the capability.
% Services with a clear defined business model: Further evaluation is required for this indicator as all the services are self-funded currently.
 The current operational status of our services is available at our public status page: status.operas-eu.org.

FitSM

2023: 37 directly personal FitSM certificates (facilitated 300+ through our facilitated trainer network) + 8 in 2024

Use case: services and the clear-defined business models
 Further evaluation is required for this indicator as all the services are self-funded currently.

Case study: Quality of the OPERAS services
 "Case study: Elaborating the quality of OPERAS services: GoTriple and the ATRIUM Researcher Forum" <https://zenodo.org/records/15672537> (page 84 - 85)

Information on reading the impact

OPERAS Service Portfolio: is an internal list including not only the services provided by OPERAS to the wider community but also internal services required to operate and coordinate the OPERAS research infrastructure.

OPERAS services in evaluation: refers to the set of services offered by OPERAS that are currently being tested, assessed, or reviewed to determine their: Usefulness, Usability, Effectiveness, Relevance to the research community and Impact on scholarly communication practices.

FitSM®: is a training and certification program in lightweight service management mainly for OPERAS members, see www.fitsm.eu.

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Objective 5. OPERAS members and communities are trained and knowledgeable in SSH FAIR and Open Science practices

Training

Use case: Uptake of FAIR principles

Data collection for this indicator is currently not feasible and requires further evaluation

Objective 6
Pillar: Fostering Quality

Objective 6. OPERAS members are trained and knowledgeable in SSH open science service delivery

Service delivery

Information on reading the impact

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Objective 7. OPERAS as a trusted advisor for national and European OS strategies

Scientific advisor and engagement with policymakers

Case study: Example of consultation

Case study: The PALOMERA validation process. <https://zenodo.org/records/15672537> (page 86 - 87)

Case study: Notable changes in policy decisions

The impact of OPERAS activities on notable changes in policy decisions cannot be validated enough at the moment. But it is under constant evaluation and will be conducted within the next 2-3 years.

Case study: OPERAS impactful publications

See Key Publications in the OPERAS annual report 2024: <https://zenodo.org/records/15672537> (page 93 - 94)

Engagement with key initiatives

Case study: Boards and task forces of which OPERAS is a member

OPERAS already conducted a “USE CASE: Boards and task forces of which OPERAS is a member” for the annual report 2023, see: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11349719> (page 67) .

Information on reading the impact

Monitoring Framework: OPERAS has established a monitoring framework within the OPERAS-PLUS project, aligned with its objectives for 2023–2025. The framework is under constant development and uses 2023 as its starting point, as data from earlier periods is incomplete. The monitoring of impact includes various indicators, as well as case studies and use cases that have been conducted or are planned. See also: D8.2: <https://zenodo.org/records/8289250> and D8.7: <https://zenodo.org/records/1693374444> of OPERAS-PLUS.

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Objective 8. Academic books are included in the Open Science policies

A set of recommendations and resources provided to support institutional strategies and funder policies for open access books

Case study: Examples on how recommendations are used

Case study: OPERAS already conducted a “USE CASE: How recommendations are used?” for the annual report 2023, see on page 66: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11349719>.

Objective 9 Pillar: Empowering Community

Objective 9. Setting up a pan-European OPERAS innovation lab

Innovation

Case study:

All case studies of the innovation lab can be found here: <https://lab.operas-eu.org/category/observatory/innovation-lab-case-study/>.

Information on reading the impact

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